

Adsorption-desorption of carbofuran in soils

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The results of these studies showed that adsorption of carbofuran on Fe-, Mn- and Cu-saturated soils increased upto the pH 6 and thereafter decreased. The values of $1/n$ which reflects the curvature in the adsorption isotherms were more than unity indicating a 'S' type of isotherm. Adsorption followed the order : black > red > alluvial soil. The order of adsorption in presence of different transitional metals was : Fe- > Mn- > Cu-. The adsorption varied directly with the effective ionic radii of exchangeable cations and inversely with increase in temperature. With the addition of sewage-sludge adsorption also increased. The enthalpy change (ΔH°) denoted that the process was exothermic and adsorption of carbofuran gave rise to entropy loss. Various studies i.e. IR, thermodynamic parameters and Freundlich adsorption isotherms revealed the existence of co-ordination between exchangeable cation of soil and oxygen of >C=O group of carbofuran.

Adsorption influences almost all the reactions of pesticides in soil. Due to adsorption, the added pesticide loses its bio-activity, resists the movement, and hence prevents the chemical from reaching the target. The adsorbed compound persists in soil for a longer period which causes pollution problems. Adsorption-desorption process in soil depends on temperature, composition and pH of soil solution^{1,2}. Sewage-sludge is applied in soil for increasing soil fertility. Pesticides applied to such soils thus interacts with sewage-sludge which affects the mechanism of adsorption phenomena. Availability of applied pesticides for plant uptake, movement in soils, chemical persistence and biological efficacy mainly depends on adsorption-desorption processes of the soil.

The purpose of the present work was to study the influence of pH, temperature, sewage-sludge, transition metal cations on the nature of adsorption and desorption of carbofuran on black, red and alluvial soils.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH : The adsorption of carbofuran on Fe-, Mn- and Cu-saturated soils increased upto the pH 6 and thereafter decreased (Fig. 1). The formation of H^+ -pesticide or Na^+ -pesticide complexes in solution may inhibit adsorption of carbofuran on the soil surface. Thus, in the absence of H^+ or Na^+ at pH 6 direct association of carbofuran with cation on the soil surface probably occurs showing maximum adsorption. Similar results are reported by other workers^{3,4}.

Sorption : Freundlich adsorption equation, $\log C = \log K + 1/n \log C_e$, where C is amount adsorbed, C_e is equilibrium concentration, K and $1/n$ constants, was used to describe carbofuran adsorption on soils. The values of $1/n$, which reflects the curvature in the adsorption isotherm were more than unity (Table 1) indicating a 'S' type of isotherm as defined by Giles *et al.*^{5,6}. A representative set of curves for adsorption isotherms on black soil is shown in Fig. 2. It indicated that new sites became available to the solvent as

Table 1. Freundlich adsorption isotherm constants of carbofuran adsorption on Fe-, Mn- and Cu-soils at different temperatures

Saturating cation	Temp. (°C)	Black soil		Red soil		Alluvial soil	
		$K \pm s$	$1/n \pm s$	$K \pm s$	$1/n \pm s$	$K \pm s$	$1/n \pm s$
Fe	25	14.2 ± 0.6	1.21 ± 0.01	13.2 ± 0.2	1.18 ± 0.02	11.8 ± 0.3	1.16 ± 0.02
	35	13.1 ± 0.5	1.14 ± 0.01	12.4 ± 0.2	1.14 ± 0.01	11.0 ± 0.3	1.12 ± 0.01
	45	12.2 ± 0.4	1.10 ± 0.02	11.7 ± 0.3	1.11 ± 0.1	10.4 ± 0.2	1.09 ± 0.02
Mn	25	13.3 ± 0.5	1.16 ± 0.02	12.6 ± 0.4	1.15 ± 0.01	11.2 ± 0.3	1.13 ± 0.01
	35	12.6 ± 0.4	1.12 ± 0.01	12.0 ± 0.1	1.11 ± 0.01	10.7 ± 0.2	1.10 ± 0.01
	45	12.0 ± 0.3	1.08 ± 0.01	11.2 ± 0.2	1.09 ± 0.01	10.2 ± 0.2	1.07 ± 0.01
Cu	25	12.8 ± 0.4	1.13 ± 0.02	12.0 ± 0.2	1.12 ± 0.2	10.7 ± 0.2	1.10 ± 0.1
	35	12.0 ± 0.3	1.10 ± 0.01	11.6 ± 0.2	1.08 ± 0.01	10.3 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.02
	45	11.5 ± 0.4	1.07 ± 0.01	10.8 ± 0.1	1.05 ± 0.02	10.0 ± 0.1	1.02 ± 0.01

(± s) are standard error of estimate.

Table 2. Freundlich and thermodynamic parameters for carbofuran adsorption on Fe-, Mn- and Cu-soils in presence of sewage sludge at 25°C

Saturating cation	Amount of sewage sludge g kg ⁻¹ soil	Black soil				Red soil				Alluvial soil			
		K ± s	1/n ± s	K ^o	ΔG ^o kJ mol ⁻¹	K ± s	1/n ± s	K ^o	ΔG ^o kJ mol ⁻¹	K ± s	1/n ± s	K ^o	ΔG ^o kJ mol ⁻¹
Fe	0	14.2 ± 0.6	1.21 ± 0.01	128.3	-12.0	13.2 ± 0.2	1.18 ± 0.02	119.6	-11.9	11.8 ± 0.3	1.16 ± 0.02	103.2	-11.5
	1	15.2 ± 0.5	1.28 ± 0.02	142.6	-12.3	14.2 ± 0.2	1.23 ± 0.01	136.8	-12.2	12.7 ± 0.3	1.21 ± 0.01	120.6	-11.9
	2	16.1 ± 0.5	1.32 ± 0.01	160.2	-12.6	15.1 ± 0.2	1.28 ± 0.02	152.4	-12.5	13.9 ± 0.4	1.27 ± 0.02	138.9	-12.2
Mn	0	13.3 ± 0.5	1.16 ± 0.02	117.3	-11.8	12.6 ± 0.4	1.15 ± 0.01	109.2	-11.6	11.2 ± 0.3	1.13 ± 0.01	95.2	-11.3
	1	14.6 ± 0.4	1.21 ± 0.01	136.8	-12.2	13.7 ± 0.3	1.20 ± 0.01	125.8	-12.0	12.0 ± 0.2	1.17 ± 0.02	112.8	-11.7
	2	15.5 ± 0.5	1.27 ± 0.01	148.7	-12.4	14.9 ± 0.4	1.24 ± 0.01	139.9	-12.2	13.0 ± 0.3	1.22 ± 0.01	130.2	-12.1
Cu	0	12.8 ± 0.4	1.13 ± 0.02	106.1	-11.4	12.0 ± 0.2	1.12 ± 0.01	100.2	-11.5	10.7 ± 0.2	1.10 ± 0.01	86.0	-11.0
	1	13.7 ± 0.4	1.17 ± 0.02	121.2	-11.9	12.9 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.01	117.7	-11.8	11.6 ± 0.2	1.14 ± 0.01	102.1	-11.5
	2	14.9 ± 0.4	1.23 ± 0.01	139.8	-12.2	13.8 ± 0.3	1.21 ± 0.01	130.1	-12.1	12.7 ± 0.2	1.19 ± 0.02	121.6	-11.9

(± s) are standard error of estimate.

Table 3. Desorption of carbofuran from Fe-, Mn- and Cu-saturated soil-carbofuran complex

	Amount of carbofuran desorbed μg g ⁻¹ soil								
	Black soil			Red soil			Alluvial soil		
	Fe-	Mn-	Cu-	Fe-	Mn-	Cu-	Fe-	Mn-	Cu-
Water	625	600	590	585	570	550	560	540	530
KCl	1050	980	900	960	900	850	900	830	800
BaCl ₂	1390	1200	1050	1070	1000	940	980	935	885

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for carbofuran adsorption on Fe-, Mn-, Cu-saturated black soil at 25°, 35° and 45°C

Soil	Saturating cation	Equilibrium constant K _o			ΔG ^o kJ mol ⁻¹			ΔH ^o kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS ^o J mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹
		25°C	35°C	45°C	25°C	35°C	45°C		
Black	Fe-	128.3	103.2	83.8	-12.02	-11.87	-11.71	-16.78 ± 0.15	-15.94 ± 0.32
	Mn-	117.3	96.1	80.0	-11.81	-11.69	-11.59	-14.99 ± 0.06	-10.69 ± 0.14
	Cu-	106.1	88.8	75.2	-11.42	-11.49	-11.42	-13.56 ± 0.02	-6.86 ± 0.16
Red	Fe-	119.6	95.8	77.7	-11.86	-11.68	-11.51	-16.99 ± 0.06	-17.23 ± 0.16
	Mn-	109.2	87.2	70.6	-11.63	-11.44	-11.26	-17.18 ± 0.02	-18.63 ± 0.06
	Cu-	100.2	81.6	66.2	-11.46	-11.27	-11.09	-17.01 ± 0.02	-18.61 ± 0.08
Alluvial	Fe-	103.2	82.0	66.1	-11.49	-11.29	-11.09	-17.54 ± 0.01	-20.34 ± 0.05
	Mn-	95.2	76.2	61.8	-11.29	-11.10	-10.91	-17.02 ± 0.02	-19.22 ± 0.09
	Cu-	86.0	69.2	56.2	-11.04	-10.82	-10.61	-16.77 ± 0.10	-19.30 ± 0.16

adsorption occurred, and there was competition of solvent for the sites on the adsorbing surface. Similar results was reported by Bansal³. Adsorption of carbofuran followed the order : black > red > alluvial soil. The order of adsorption in presence of different transitional metals was : Fe- > Mn- > Cu-, which was in accordance with effective ionic radii of exchangeable cations, supported by values of Freundlich constant *K* and *1/n* (Table 1).

Effect of temperature : An increase in temperature from 25 to 45°C resulted in a decrease of adsorption of carbofuran (supported by Freundlich constants) that may be due to : (i) decrease in physical adsorption⁷ caused by weakening of van der Waal's forces of attraction between

carbofuran and soil surface⁸, and (ii) a change in solubility of pesticides with a change in temperature⁹.

Effect of sewage-sludge : The adsorption of carbofuran on soil samples with sewage-sludge followed the Freundlich equation. The values are given in Table 2. The adsorption increased with the addition of sewage-sludge. It may be caused by the interaction of pesticides with organic-matter added in soil as sewage-sludge, via multiple binding mechanisms including ionic bond between organic matter and carbofuran and/or hydrogen bonds in between pesticides and organic-matter¹⁰. The effect of sewage-sludge on three different soil was almost the same denoting same mechanism of adsorption.

Desorption studies : The results of desorption (Table 3) indicated that part of carbofuran adsorbed on Fe-, Mn- and Cu-saturated soils may be desorbed by water or solutions of inorganic salts. The desorption was more in salt solution than by distilled water which could be due to : (i) flocculation resulting from polymer bridges between the mineral particles in suspension¹¹, and (ii) coagulation effect on dispersed solids because of the decrease in electrical double layer at the interface solution-dispersed particle¹². From the results it may be inferred that adsorption of carbofuran occurred appreciably by ionic interactions and long range attractive forces at crystal edge, and crystal basal surface.

Table 5. Physical and chemical properties of the soils and sewage-sludge

Properties	Types of soils			
	Black (Vertisol)	Red (Alfisol)	Alluvial (Inceptisol)	Sewage-sludge
Sand (%)	3.0	33.9	54.4	-
Silt (%)	16.0	47.7	42.6	-
Clay (%)	81.0	18.4	3.0	-
Soil pH	7.6	7.2	8.1	7.6
Organic matter (g kg ⁻¹)	18.8	8.1	8.6	186.0
Water holding capacity (%)	70	42	36	-
CEC [c mol(p ⁺)kg ⁻¹]	9.75	6.07	6.00	-
EC (m mhos/cm)	2.3	0.3	0.2	1.9
Total heavy metals (µg g ⁻¹)				
Zn	6.8	6.3	6.2	540.0
Cu	1.8	1.4	1.4	306.0
Mn	32	30	32	600.0
Fe	2100	2600	2000	2010.0
Cr	4.6	3.6	4.0	42.0
Ni	0.6	0.4	0.5	24.0
Pb	1.6	1.6	1.7	76.0
Cd	0.12	Traces	Traces	3.0
DTPA extractable heavy metals (µg g ⁻¹)				
Zn	0.68	0.66	0.42	-
Cu	0.68	0.60	0.64	-
Mn	3.0	2.6	2.8	-
Fe	8.8	18.8	3.8	-
Cr	0.22	0.2	0.2	-
Ni	0.02	0.02	0.04	-
Pb	0.03	0.06	0.04	-
Cd	0.02	Traces	Traces	-

From the adsorption curves the values of thermodynamic parameters viz. K_0 , ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 , ΔS^0 were calculated using Biggar and Cheung method¹³ as discussed elsewhere³. The values are given in Table 1.

The values of K_0 which were found to be more than one, are indicative of the fact that carbofuran had a higher preference on soil surface and the adsorption decreased in the order ; Fe- > Mn- > and Cu-soil. The values of K_0 were in order : black soil > red soil > alluvial soil. These data support our earlier deductions regarding the order of adsorption. The value of K_0 decrease with temperature and in-

creased on adding sewage-sludge (Table 2), suggesting that the adsorption decreased with the rise in temperature but there was an increase in the presence of sewage-sludge.

The values of ΔG^0 were negative in the range of -12.02 to -10.6 kJ and increased with rise in temperature pointing towards spontaneity of the reaction with a greater affinity for carbofuran by soil. The values of ΔG^0 were higher in presence of sewage-sludge (Table 4) than in unamended soils, indicating a higher affinity of the soils for carbofuran in presence of sewage-sludge than in unamended soils.

The value of ΔH^0 denoted the exothermic nature of the reaction and that the adsorption was energetically stable. The values of ΔH^0 also showed that adsorption took place through bonding mechanism¹⁴. The values of ΔS^0 for carbofuran adsorption clearly indicated that entropy change associated with adsorption were the driving force for the adsorption reaction. As carbofuran molecules, adsorbed on the soil surface, had fewer translational and rotational degrees of freedom than carbofuran molecule in solution, resulted negative entropy changes¹⁵.

From the above studies it may be inferred that the adsorption of carbofuran might be due to coordination be-

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on carbofuran adsorption on soil.

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherms of carbofuran adsorption on black soil.

tween exchangeable transition metal-cation and oxygen of the amide group either directly or through water molecules³.

These mechanisms are very well supported by IR studies. A shift of bands at 1680 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu = -20$ to -25 cm^{-1}) attributed to a $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations, at 1390 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu = +15$ to $+20\text{ cm}^{-1}$) attributing to C–N stretching during complexation on the carbofuran with soils were recorded.

Experimental

Three surface-soils (0–25 cm) viz. black, red and alluvial, collected from different parts of India were selected for the study. The physico-chemical properties of soil and untreated sewage sludge determined by usual methods are given in Table 5.

The effect of pH on adsorption was investigated at eight different pH, ranging from 2–12, maintained by 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH. 10 g of soil solution and 100 mL of standard carbofuran solution ($500\text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) were taken in several glass stoppered conical flasks and volume was made 250 mL with distilled water. The samples were shaken for 30 h and centrifuged, carbofuran in supernatant was estimated spectrophotometrically¹⁶. The amount of carbofuran adsorbed was obtained by difference from the amount added and the amount remained. To study the effect of temperature, adsorption was measured with variable amounts (0–100 mL) of carbofuran ($500\text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at 25, 35, 45 \pm 0.5°C with Fe-, Mn- and Cu-saturated soil samples.

The influence of sewage-sludge on adsorption was studied at 25 \pm 0.5°C by adding 100 and 200 mg of sewage sludge to each of 10 g of Fe-, Mn- and Cu-saturated soil samples used for adsorption. The amount of pesticide in supernatant was estimated as discussed earlier.

For the desorption experiments, 10 g of the soil was shaken with 100 mL of carbofuran ($500\text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 30 h after making the solution to 250 mL, then the suspensions were centrifuged. The whole of the supernatant solution was withdrawn and aliquots were taken for the determination of carbofuran adsorbed. The soil samples were treated

with water, 50 mL of 0.02 M KCl or 50 mL of 0.01 M CaCl_2 respectively, the volume was adjusted to 250 mL with distilled water, shaken for 30 h and centrifuged as above. 100 mL of supernatant was withdrawn and retained soil samples were treated again with 100 mL of water, KCl or CaCl_2 shaken for 30 h, centrifuged and carbofuran in both of the supernatant solutions was estimated.

IR analyses of soils and their complex samples were performed as discussed elsewhere¹⁷.

All the experiments were done in triplicate with suitable blanks.

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